

7th International Symposium on Surface Imaging/Spectroscopy at the Solid/Liquid Interface

JUNE 5th – 7th, 2024, Kraków, Poland

organized by

**Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry
Polish Academy of Sciences
and
Faculty of Chemistry of the Jagiellonian University**

Book of Abstracts

Scientific Committee

Magdalena Dudek, AGH, Poland
Krzysztof Fic, PUT, Poland
Halina Krawiec, AGH, Poland
Cheng-Xin Li, Xi'an JU, China
Jacek Ryl, GUT, Poland
Wojciech Simka, SUT, Poland
Grzegorz D. Sulka, JU, Poland
Piotr Warszyński, ICSC PAS, Poland
Małgorzata Witko, ICSC PAS, Poland
Leszek Zaraska, JU, Poland
Małgorzata Zimowska, ICSC PAS, Poland

Organizing Committee

Agnieszka Brzózka, JU, Poland
Magdalena Gurgul, JU, Poland
Joanna Kapusta-Kołodziej, JU, Poland
Dzmitry Kharytonau, ICSC PAS, Poland
Grzegorz Mordarski, ICSC PAS, Poland
Michał Mosiałek, ICSC PAS, Poland
Konrad Skowron, ICSC PAS, Poland
Piotr Skowron, ICSC PAS, Poland
Robert P. Socha, ICSC PAS, Poland
Grzegorz D. Sulka, JU, Poland, Organizer
Karolina Syrek, JU, Poland
Piotr Warszyński, ICSC PAS, Poland, Chair
Leszek Zaraska, JU, Poland
Małgorzata Zimowska, ICSC PAS, Poland, Co-organizer

Editors

Grzegorz Mordarski, ICSC PAS, Poland
Piotr Skowron, ICSC PAS, Poland

These conference materials were prepared in the form sent by participants.
The Organizers and Editors are not responsible for the content of the abstracts.

Copyright © 2024

**Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry
Polish Academy of Sciences
2024, Kraków, Poland**

ISBN 978-83-60514-38-2

Influence of Surface Nanocrystallization of Mg Substrate on Structure and Corrosion Resistance of Phosphate Conversion Coatings

K. Skowron¹, G. Mordarski¹, D. Kharytonau¹, E. Dryzek², M. Zimowska¹

(1) *Jerzy Haber Institute of Catalysis and Surface Chemistry, Polish Academy of Sciences, Niezapominajek 8, PL–30239 Kraków, Poland*

(2) *Institute of Nuclear Physics Polish Academy of Sciences, PL–31342 Kraków, Poland*

Magnesium alloys are a convenient choice for temporary implant applications due to their broad range of advantages, including excellent biocompatibility and osseointegration [1]. Nevertheless, the attempts to use magnesium as a biomaterial have proved to be challenging due to its relatively high corrosion rate in a human body environment [2]. Therefore, the surface of Mg implants should be modified to provide a possibility for controllable degradation. Phosphate conversion coatings (PCCs) attracted attention due to their biocompatibility and environment–friendly characteristics [3].

The corrosion resistance of PCCs depends on the surface morphology, i.e. roughness and crystallite size [4]. Increasing the number of grain boundaries and structural defects present at the Mg substrate leads to a simultaneous increase in the number of nucleation spots for phosphate crystals. Hence, the implementation of severe plastic deformation (SPD) pre–treatment strategies is promising for grain refinement and the introduction of crystal lattice defects in the Mg surface, which will improve the properties of the formed protective PCCs [5]. Since surface pre–treatment based on SPD introduces a large amount of crystal lattice defects and greatly reduces the grain size in the surface layer, hence such a treatment will accelerate the nucleation of phosphate crystals and allow to control of the morphology of the formed PCCs and their degradation profile.

The aim of this study is to investigate the impact of Mg substrate nanocrystallization on the deposition kinetics and corrosion protection of phosphate layers. The microstructure and corrosion resistance of the as–prepared systems are discussed. To minimize the impact of alloying additives and impurities on the surface crystallization, and to facilitate the interpretation and correlation of the obtained results, commercial purity (CP) Mg was used. The surface mechanical attrition treatment (SMAT) method was used to modify the structure of the Mg substrate. SMAT is a cold working method that belongs to the surface self–nanocrystallisation methods, which are carried out without changing the chemical phase composition of the substrate [6]. Changes in the SMAT process parameters i.e. shots size, and time of the process resulted in obtaining surfaces characterized by different structures. Two different types of PCCs were obtained: magnesium phosphate and calcium phosphate. Conversion layers were deposited on the SMAT–treated high–purity Mg samples and as–polished reference ones. A set of spectroscopic and microscopic techniques was used to characterize the surface before and after SPD treatment and PCC deposition.

References

- [1] V. Tsakiris, C. Tardei, F.M. Clicinschi, J. Magnes. Alloy., 2021;9:1884–905
- [2] K. Kumar, R.S Gill, U. Batra, Mater Technol. 2018;33(2):153–172
- [3] J.E. Gray, B. Luan, J. Alloys Compd., 2002;336:88–113
- [4] Q Li, S Xu, J Hu, S Zhang, X Zhong, X Yang, Electrochim Acta. 2010;55(3):887–894
- [5] M Kasaeian–Naeini, M Sedighi, R Hashemi, J. Magnes. Alloy., 2022;10:938–55
- [6] LU Ke, LU Jian, J Mater Sci Technol, 1999;15(03): 193–197

Acknowledgement

Konrad Skowron gratefully acknowledges financial support from the National Science Center (Poland) under research Grant Miniatura 7 no. 2023/07/X/ST11/00036